

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Breunig**FIRST NAME:** Maria Magdalena**PROGRAM CODE:** MIPH**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** GULMA**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MS Word 2019 on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Building a fundament
2. Structuring written assignments (EUCLID 2019, 1–4)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5–13)
4. Academic language rules for proficient non-academic language users (EUCLID 2019, 17–23)
5. Style Guidelines (EUCLID 2019, 24–26)
6. American versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27–35)
7. Internalizing the culture of academic writing (EUCLID 2019, 1–61)

STUDYING THE CULTURE OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) **BUILDING THE FOUNDATIONS**

Writing in English is something I do every day. In my work as well as in my private life, I am writing in different levels of professionalism: work emails, official statements, legal documents, as well as many personal texts. Also, in academic writing, I became trained and proficient, thanks to my bachelor's degree. Nevertheless, by starting a master's program in MIPH, I face a new challenge of writing many high-quality academic papers. This module will aim to advance my writing skills to a new level and develop real expertise in producing good content and excellent style.

Therefore, I aim to gain a good foundation of rules and characteristics of academic writing from the provided materials. I am hoping to strengthen my language skills and understand the regulations specific to EUCLID requirements. In the following chapters, I will discuss a selection of topics from the provided materials' in detail to obtain maximum learning outcomes.

2) STRUCTURING WRITTEN ASSIGNMENTS

The biggest obstacle to overcome in academic writing for me has always been to overcome the anxiety of a big piece of work that has to be conducted without further structuring through an external system, like lectures or sub-assignments. Therefore, chapter one has been beneficial to me. It summarizes how writing an assignment can be broken down into clear and manageable steps (EUCLID 2019, 1–4).

I found it helpful to be reminded of the tone and character of academic writing/writing academically. Unlike in other literature types, it is interesting to start the writing process not with the introduction but with the body and add the personal reflections in the introduction and conclusion afterwards. Furthermore, I learned anew to approach essay writing as an ongoing process, which helps prevent writers from a block and the blanc page's fear.

Unfortunately, the links to further reading on 'assignment planning' and 'effective note-making from written text' are not available on the LMS platform (EUCLID 2019, 1–2). This is the first inconsistency that came to my attention and was followed by others throughout the paper, which I will analyze in the upcoming chapters.

After describing how to write and structure an academic essay in Chapter one, it is crucial to analyze the opposite question of how not to write in an academic setting and which rules are to be obeyed. Thus, the following chapter will focus on plagiarism.

3) PLAGIARISM

I have greatly benefitted from the descriptions in the chapter on plagiarism. This chapter has provided an extensive summary of plagiarism, what it includes, what plagiarism does not include and why it is a serious academic offence. It touches on how to practically avoid plagiarizing structurally, whereas the technical detail on how exactly to quote different sources is described in chapter 8. For future assignments in this master's program, I am glad to have this chapter at hand as an outline of the concept of plagiarism and to learn a structure on how to avoid that offence (EUCLID 2019, 5–13).

However, it has not answered all of my concerns regarding plagiarism. In my experience of academic writing, it is evident and straight forward not to use other authors' information without citing their work since that would be a fraud. For me, the struggle of avoiding plagiarism begins when I already have specific information about this topic (for example, from previous reading or lectures) but do not know the exact source. Even in the first chapter of the coursepack, the author mentions that the student is not supposed to take notes at the time of first reading into the topic (EUCLID 2019, 2). If then, weeks later, when formulating the paper, I, as a student, remember a certain fact that cannot be considered general knowledge, it is challenging to track down this one statement from hundreds of early reading pages. This experience has taught me to challenge the advice of not taking notes and always keep a detailed register of my sources. This structure helps me

save valuable energy and time on skimming through materials repetitively to find the source of an already known fact or idea.

Another detail that needs clarification for me is the subchapter 'More about Citations' on page 12. The author states the recommended number of citations for certain types of papers. Concretely, he advises to use one citation in response papers or reading journals, but two to three citations in mid-term or final exams. This attracted my attention since, in my understanding of academic research and writing, many more than just two or three sources of information are needed. Contradicting above, the checklist for response papers provided by EUCLID demands at least 5-7 references from the provided materials and gives the option of quoting additional relevant sources if necessary (Euclid University 2020, 2). Comparatively, the student orientation article discusses the use of three references per page in a research paper (EUCLID 2019, 7–8). Still, it remains unclear what the chapter 'More about Citations' recommends, and in my opinion, further explanation is needed. Specifically, which of the rules of thumb mentioned above the students should apply regarding an approximate number of citations in a paper or response paper.

Despite the minor criticism, I am glad to strengthen my understanding of academic writings and its critical points through this paper. Plagiarism is emphasized as one of the main aspects to distinguish between academic and other kinds of literature.

4) ACADEMIC LANGUAGE RULES FOR PROFICIENT NON-ACADEMIC LANGUAGE USERS

Continuing in the above's thought of improving my understanding of the overall culture of academic writing and writing in a formal setting in general, chapter four is indispensable to me. I am a non-native English speaker but have grown to use English as my primary language in daily life throughout the last decade. In my opinion, using a language all day and in different situations of everyday life is the best way to become truly proficient in a foreign language. At the same time, it brings its disadvantages since the advancements in language do not come from an official source and are subject to dialect and the common mistakes of the colloquial use of the language. Therefore, naming and clarifying a long list of these common mistakes has been precisely the type of English language training I needed to prepare myself for more academic writing.

Apart from the useful content of chapter four, it marks a change in style in the paper. The first three chapters are written in a more formal, birds-eye view perspective. In chapter four, the author describes his personal memories and refers to the group of readers and himself as "we" (EUCLID 2019, 23). This creates a more informal but at the same time relatable character to the paper. Throughout the subsequent chapters, the author continues changing the narrative between the third person (EUCLID 2019, 22) the first person (EUCLID 2019, 23) and directly addressing the reader in the second person with "you" (EUCLID 2019, 26).

This detail of changing perspectives attracted my attention before reaching chapter five, which describes the need for style guidelines. Having found this inconsistency increased my interest in style guidelines since I had experienced how a changing style can interrupt the reading process. In the next chapter, I will analyze further reflections on guidelines regarding style.

5) STYLE GUIDELINES

On page 24 and 25, the author defines and describes a style guide and argues for its profitability. According to this definition, the coursepack itself qualifies as a style manuscript. Nevertheless, the author advises the student to follow the Turabian style and references to external sources. This sparked me to reflect on the author's incentive to refer to the Turabian style instead of prompting the students to follow the coursepack's rules.

Mainly, it could stem from the need for a more official style for a high-quality university course, and therefore following the academic ideal of following renowned ways of conducting research. On the other hand, it gives the additional task to the student, to compare the rules of the ACA-401 coursepack with the Turabian style and find their way to incorporate both of them.

Having looked into the Chicago Manual of Style – also referred to as Turabian - it is valuable as a style manuscript, demonstrating the use of abbreviations, numbers, dates etc., as listed in chapter eight of the coursepack (EUCLID 2019, 44–55). Furthermore, it also fulfils the role of a set of rules for quoting and technically formatting, as Benett College displays clearly on their website (The University of Chicago Press 2012). It should be kept at hand to use quotations correctly during written assignments.

As correctness and consistency are essential measurements of quality academic work, correct citations have to be complemented by correctness in language and consistency in dialects. Therefore, in the next chapter, I will reflect on the distinguishment between American and British English.

6) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

I have been studying and advancing in my English language skills for two decades. Firstly, learning English as a second language in school and then improving it during my bachelor's course and through my private life, where English has been my first language for many years. I never received educational information about British Standard English and American Standard English's official differences in all these years. My exposure to the English language's different accents has mainly been through mass media, as it is also described in chapter six of the coursepack (EUCLID 2019, 27). Therefore, distinguishing between the different sets of rules has always proven to be a struggle for me in formal writing. With chapter six of the coursepack, I am glad to have a detailed set of rules at hand that I will use extensively throughout the upcoming assignments to harmonize my English

language skill for the correct usage of the American Standard English (EUCLID 2019, 27–35).

Having said this, the author's explanations reduce throughout the chapter so that towards the end of the chapter, it is a mere listing of different options. For example, I would like to analyze the sub-section "The writing of dates" (EUCLID 2019, 35). The author lists several examples of writing dates without assigning them to either British or American English. Within a bracket, he poses the question of comprehensibility since the number showing the day and the number indicating the month can be interchanged in their sequence. The author gives no further recommendations or comments. Nevertheless, reading the chapter has taught me to distinguish between different wording, setting punctuation, and differences in grammar and spelling. The chapter has succeeded in teaching the reader to stay consistent in American Standard English, which is an essential aspect of this assignment's learning outcomes.

In the last chapter, I will summarize Period one's overall learning outcomes while referring to my personal starting point and challenges.

7) INTERNALISING THE CULTURE OF ACADEMIC WRITING

Starting the Masters in International Public Health has been a long-awaited dream for me. After years of working within the healthcare sector in different countries, I have felt the need to improve my knowledge of public health in an academic setting. Finally, I had the time and resources to go back to university, and after months of researching, writing applications and preparing, my eagerness to dive into the critical topics of international global health is at an ever-high.

Having said this, my first reaction to begin this new chapter with working through a whole module of academic writing was little enthusiastic. I had been extensively trained in the rules of academic writing through my Bachelors of Science program in Midwifery and felt that there are more exciting topics to learn about but the rules of punctuation and quotation.

Nevertheless, it took me only a few moments to read and listen to the provided materials to understand the importance and logic of starting this module. Preparing for this response paper, I became aware of how fundamental it is to first understand the concept of academic learning before beginning to learn the actual content. I got reminded of how different the approach is towards grasping a topic from an academic standpoint than gathering information in my daily life. Consequently, I started approaching this module with new interest since it gives me a chance to improve my writing skills to succeed in the master's program and advance in professional writing. My personal challenge in this module will be to enhance my writing skills from a bachelor's level to one appropriate for a master's program. This concerns content, style and language since I studied my bachelor's

in my mother tongue, German. In contrast, I am now eager to advance to professional academic writing in English.

Beyond my personal benefits, which I quickly asserted while working through the materials, I also understood that I am privileged to participate in such an international course with a highly diverse body of students coming from various educational systems. Therefore, it is imperative to unite the diversity of styles and experiences and give all EUCID students a united tool at hand.

In summary, having worked through the provided videos and the coursepack ACA-401, I feel more secure in working with the provided tools: the word templates and checklist on response papers, Zotero as a citation software and the online forums used by EUCLID. My understanding of the mindset of academic research and writing and the importance of correctness and consistency have been strengthened. I am aware that plagiarism is a severe academic offence but learned how to avoid plagiarism through correct citation methods. Beyond being more aware of the academic concepts explained above, I will continue keeping the coursepack at hand to use it as a work of reference for my future assignments.

REFERENCES

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